

'FLUIDITY TEMPERATURE' OF SOME HOMOLOGOUS SERIES

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The significance of T_s , the temperature of fluidity, has been brought out, and $e^{\alpha T_s}$ has been shown to be equal to the ratio of the average volume of a molecule, which the molecule possesses when its fluid properties just appear, to the actual volume of the molecule. This has been established in the case of some homologous series from data available in the literature.

In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 493) an equation relating fluidity (ϕ) of a liquid with its coefficient of thermal expansion (α) has been derived from considerations based upon Batschinski's equation (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1913, 84, 643) and also upon the assumption of the free volume in liquids as enunciated by Eyring (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 283). This equation yields a linear plot of ϕ against $e^{\alpha T}$, where T represents the relevant temperature and α , the coefficient of expansion. The equation is of the form :

$$e^{\alpha T_s} + \frac{e^{\alpha T_s}}{C.V_s} \phi = e^{\alpha T} - a + b\phi \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where a stands for $e^{\alpha T_s}$ and b , for $e^{\alpha T_s} / C.V_s$

In this derivation the concept of a temperature T_s has been introduced for the first time apparently for mathematical simplification. This particular temperature T_s represents the threshold temperature at which a liquid loses its free volume and becomes too compact to have any fluidity. This temperature therefore marks the limit from where the fluidity of any liquid starts and can thus be rightly designated as the "temperature of fluidity" for the particular substance.

It was also observed in the same communication (*loc. cit.*) that the straight lines obtained by plotting ϕ against $e^{\alpha T}$, according to equation (1) above, converged to the same point on the $e^{\alpha T}$ -axis for members of the same homologous series. As many as five different homologous series were reported therein and graphical representations of two of them shown. Another interesting feature which was noticed was that for all the series reported therein, the points of convergence were close to each other, being in the neighbourhood of $e^{\alpha T_s} = 1.25$. This striking feature, hit upon by chance, was suggestive of some important significance on the part of this particular temperature. In the present paper this aspect has been further developed and critically examined with reference to a few more homologous series and a theoretical interpretation attempted.

EXPERIMENTAL

The cases of normal olefines and thiols-2 have been studied besides the cases of n -paraffins, n -alkylbenzenes, n -alkyl cyclohexanes, n -alkyl cyclo-

pentanes, and *n*-mercaptans, which have been reported in a preliminary manner in the earlier communication referred to above (*loc. cit.*). They are graphically

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The points of convergence on the $e^{\alpha T}$ -axis, referred to as $e^{\alpha T^0}$ have been summarised in the following table.

TABLE I

Homologous series.	Point of convergence on $e^{\alpha T}$ -axis ($= e^{\alpha T^0}$)
1. <i>n</i> -Paraffins	1.250
2. <i>n</i> -Alkylbenzenes	1.236
3. <i>n</i> -Alkyl cyclopentanes	1.252
4. <i>n</i> -Alkyl cyclohexanes	1.252
5. <i>n</i> -Mercaptans	
(a) Ethyl to butyl mercaptans	1.262
(b) Amyl mercaptan	1.250
(c) Hexyl to nonyl mercaptans	1.237
6. Olefines	1.250
7. Thiols-2(C ₃ to C ₉)	1.240

The relevant data for the above hydrocarbons have been collected from the "Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Hydrocarbons" published and very kindly supplied to us by the National Bureau of Standards, U.S.A. The data for *n*-mercaptans and thiols-2 have been taken from Landolt-Börnstein Tabellen. A cursory glance at the figures will impress that the values of $e^{\alpha T}$ in the different cases are quite close to each other.

DISCUSSION

Theoretical

By definition the coefficient of thermal expansion of any substance is given by

$$\alpha = \left(\frac{d \ln V}{dT} \right)_P \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (ii)$$

$$\text{whence } \ln \frac{V}{V_0} = \alpha T \text{ or } V = V_0 \cdot e^{\alpha T} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (iii)$$

A closer scrutiny brings out the significance of this V_0 to be a hypothetical volume calculated on the assumption of the independence of α on the temperature down to absolute zero ($T=0$). Equation (ii) being quite general, if we consider the liquid state of the substance in question, V_0 will stand for the imaginary volume of the liquid at absolute zero, calculated on the assumption that α remains constant and is equal to that of the liquid.

In actual cases most liquids solidify at their freezing points long before the absolute zero is reached, and the volume which it is possible to get at absolute zero by extrapolation (because attainment of absolute zero is an impossibility from thermodynamic considerations) should refer more correctly to the volume of the solid state calculated on the basis of the constancy of the coefficient of expansion of the solid down to zero temperature. Of these two volumes [viz., the volume of the liquid extrapolated to absolute zero (V_{0l}) and that of the solid state extrapolated down to the same temperature (V_{0s}) on the assumption of the constancy of their respective coefficients of expansions] both of which are imaginary, the one of the solid state will be slightly larger than the other because α for the solid is lower than that of the liquid. As a matter of approximation, these two extrapolated values may be regarded as equal to each other for all practical purposes. Thus for the hydrocarbon $C_{20}H_{42}$, whose specific volumes at different temperatures both in the solid and liquid states could be obtained from the literature, the ratio of these extrapolated values amounts to $V_{0s} : V_{0l} = 1.016 : 1$ *. Hence, passing

* These data have been obtained from "The Physical and Thermodynamic Properties of Hydrocarbons" (*loc. cit.*).

from specific to molecular volume, we can approximately accept the molecular volume V_T of a liquid at any temperature

$$V_T = V_{01} \cdot e^{\alpha T} - V_{0s} \cdot e^{\alpha T} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (iv)$$

which signifies that the molecular volume of a liquid at any temperature, T , is equal to $e^{\alpha T}$ times the volume of the same substance in the solid state at absolute zero. The equation (iv), although approximate, is a general one following directly from the definition of the coefficient of thermal expansion.

Now assuming that the fluidity of a liquid is a function of its free volume (cf. Batschinski, *loc. cit.*, Eyring and co-workers, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1937, 41, 249) we may represent it mathematically as

$$\phi = F(V_f)$$

where F stands for any function and V_f for the free volume in the sense used by Eyring (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1936, 4, 283) being the empty volume in a liquid within which the centre of a molecule can move and produce the viscous flow.

Expanding the function by McLaurin's theorem we get

$$\phi = a_0 V_f + a_1 V_f^2 + a_2 V_f^3 + a_3 V_f^4 + \dots + a_n V_f^n + \dots$$

where a_0, a_1, a_2 etc., are constants.

From calculations based upon the velocity of sound in the liquid state it has been possible to establish that

$$\phi = a_1 V_f \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (v)^*$$

all the other coefficients and indices being redundant (cf. Kincaid and Eyring, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1938, 6, 620).

If a liquid is cooled, its free volume gradually decreases till at a temperature T_s , where V_f becomes zero, the liquid loses its fluidity. Absence of free volume in a liquid does not necessarily signify that there is no empty space between liquid molecules. In fact, there may be some empty space still whose magnitude gradually diminishes as the temperature is cooled down, but the molecules cannot move within it and produce the viscous flow. The extrapolation of the volume of a liquid down to absolute zero is thus justified.

Now at T_s , where ϕ just disappears we have from equation (iv)

$$V_{T_s} = V_{0s} \cdot e^{\alpha T_s} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (vi)$$

which indicates that the fluidity of a substance starts at that temperature (T_s) where the volume of the substance becomes $e^{\alpha T_s}$ times its volume at absolute zero.

This conclusion is interesting because it leads to a rough picture of how and where the fluidity of any substance starts. Again since V_{0s} stands for

*This equation (v) will be established from experimental data in a future communication in connection with some other problem.

the molar volume of the solid at absolute zero, where the solid is expected to be in a perfect crystalline state with the highest possible close-packed structure, this may be regarded as the actual volume of all the molecules in a mole of the substance. Hence dividing V_{0s} by N , the Avogadro's number, we get approximately the actual volume of a single molecule. Similarly by dividing V_{T_s} by N we get the average volume of a molecule of the substance at temperature T_s , where its fluidity just starts. Since at T_s the close packing, which obtains at absolute zero, will be disturbed, this average volume per molecule at T_s includes the actual volume together with the empty space surrounding this. The ratio of these two, viz., the average volume of the molecule to the actual volume (as calculated from its molar volume at 0° absolute) will be equal to

$$V_{T_s}/V_{0s} = e^{\alpha T_s} \quad \text{by equation (vi)} = a, \text{ say} \quad \dots \quad \text{(vii).}$$

Thus $e^{\alpha T_s}$, which represents the intercepts in the figures (cf. equation ϵ), signifies the ratio (α) of these volumes, from which it is clear that the fluidity of a liquid will start at a temperature T_s where the average volume per molecule will be $e^{\alpha T_s}$ times its actual volume. For the aliphatic hydrocarbon chain the volume of $e^{\alpha T_s}$ has been observed to be 1.25 as shown in the table.

It may be mentioned here that the simple picture on the basis of which the foregoing relation is derived, although quite fascinating, is, however, far removed from the state of things prevailing in an actual process. The extrapolation of the fluidity lines as presented in the above figures to intersect the $e^{\alpha T}$ -axis has been carried out under two simplifying assumptions :

(i) α remains constant over the entire temperature range considered, and (ii) no other factors appear to interfere with the fluidity at these temperatures down to T_s , excepting the disappearance of the free volume of the liquid. These assumptions, however, do not conform to reality because it is well known that, at low temperatures, as molecules approach closer and closer, not only Van der Waals' force of attraction and a diminished repulsive effect due to decreased thermal agitation but also other forces which are operative in the solid state gradually make their appearance and influence the phenomenon of transition from the liquid to the solid state. Hence, a difference between the temperature of fluidity (T_s) and the actual freezing point (T_m) of a liquid is but natural and up to the expectation. But still a study of this transition in the light of the 'hole theory' is interesting as will be appreciated from the considerations set forth below.

Verification from Experimental Data

It will now be examined how far the conclusions derived from equation (vi) conform to experimentally observed facts. From surface pressure measurements the cross-section of normal paraffin chains has been calculated to be 21 sq. Å (cf. Langmuir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 361). Since the area of the cross-section is independent of the length of the hydrocarbon chain, the 21 sq. Å has been regarded as an approximate value of the cross-section of the $-\text{CH}_2$ group. X-ray observations on long chain hydrocarbons and their derivatives indicate that the area of the cross-section of this group in the crystal is about 18.5 sq. Å (vide Glasstone, "Recent Advances in Physical Chemistry", 1933, 2nd Ed., p. 332). These values of 21 sq. Å from surface films and 18.5 sq. Å for the crystalline solids may be regarded as the average cross-section of a CH_2 group in the liquid state devoid of any free volume and its actual cross-section, the former being greater because it involves some empty space as well. The cross-sections are therefore in the ratio 21 : 18.5 whence, assuming the $-\text{CH}_2$ group to be spherical, the volumes of the same group in the liquid and solid states will be related to each other (21 : 18.5) which equals 1.21. A $-\text{CH}_2$ group should thus show an increase of volume to the extent of 1.21 times that of its actual volume and any compound made up essentially of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups, like paraffin hydrocarbons, is expected to show an expansion to the same extent.

This point of view will be corroborated if, in the case of methane which is essentially composed of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups, the intercept of $(\phi - e^{\alpha T})$ line on the

FIG. 3.
Methane.

$e^{\alpha T}$ -axis agrees with this value of 1.21. The actual value amounts to 1.220 which is in excellent agreement with this value (vide Fig. 3).

Other normal hydrocarbons, however, all uniformly yield a value of 1.25 which indicates that molecules in these hydrocarbons need further separation for the appearance of fluidity. Methane is a spherically symmetrical molecule which the other members of the series are not, and it is easy to understand that in the case of spherical symmetry, the average intramolecular separation necessary for the appearance of fluidity should be less than those cases where spherical symmetry is absent. A slight difference between these values for methane (1.220 and 1.250) can thus be understood although all these hydrocarbons are essentially made up of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups.

The values of a (vide equation *vii*) as presented in Table I may find explanation in the light of the same considerations. A slightly higher or lower value observed in some series, might be attributed to the relative importance of the $-\text{CH}_2$ groups in the particular series as well as their position and orientation in determining the degree of assymetry. Thus, the lower members of the n -mercaptans exhibit greater deviation than the higher members where there is a perceptible tendency to come back to the value of 1.220 (the value of a for methane), due probably to the increase in the number of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups in the compounds.

Benzene and its homologues present points of further interest. Benzene itself yields a value of $a = 1.162$. From toluene, where at least one $-\text{CH}_2$ group is present, this ratio jumps to 1.236 which is almost equal to that of methane, but slightly lower than that of the other paraffins. It is not unlikely that this latter owes its origin to the presence of the planar benzene ring itself in the molecule. In *cyclopentane* and *cyclohexane* series (cf. Table I) the values of a equal 1.252 and, although in these compounds there are five-membered and six-membered rings, higher values of a compared to the benzene homologues may be due to the difference in the nature of these rings from that of benzene. The coincidences of the values of a , as observed in this case, with those of the normal paraffins may likewise be looked upon as an effect of the presence of $-\text{CH}_2$ groups in these, whereas in the benzene ring there is no $-\text{CH}_2$ group. The importance of $-\text{CH}_2$ group is further supported by the fact that the normal homologues of *cyclopentane* and *cyclohexane* yield $a = 1.252$ which compares favourably with $a = 1.250$ in the case of the olefine homologues. Although in the former two series there is a ring in the molecule and in the latter there is a double bond, the coincidence in the values of a for these series might be attributed to some common factor viz., the $-\text{CH}_2$ groups in these compounds.

Thus, it is evident that the obvious conclusions which can be reached on this point from evidences cited above may be summarised by the statement that fluidity in any substance becomes possible when each of its molecules remains surrounded by sufficient empty space so that one can easily slide past another. In this picture a bigger molecule may not necessarily require larger space for its movement but an assymetric molecule would require larger space than a symmetrical one and a branched chain will necessarily require wider separation from each other before it can flow without being hindered by other molecules. The ratio a ($-e^{aT}$) which is a measure of the separation necessary for the appearance of fluidity will have a higher value as the assymetry in the molecule increases. Thus, in the case of the isomers of propylbenzene, the value of a for *n*-propylbenzene equals 1.236, which is equal to that for other normal homologues of benzene, while the *isopropylbenzene*, with a $-\text{CH}_2$

group in the side, yields $a=1.248$. Again for the two isomers : 1-methyl-4-ethylbenzene and 1:2:4-trimethylbenzene, the former is symmetrical and yields a value $a=1.232$, while the latter which is lacking in symmetry shows $a=1.260$. The values of a in the case of *ortho*-, *meta*- or *para*-xylenes, all of which are symmetrical, yield $a=1.236$, the same as that of other benzene homologues. All these facts lend further corroboration to the view points presented above.

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